

A Study on the Causes of Juvenile Delinquency in Children and its Prevention in India

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Abstract The problem of juvenile delinquency has become a very serious problem in today's time, which is increasing with time. The concept of juvenile delinquency is not new, we see and hear incidents related to juvenile delinquents around us in the news and social media. The purpose of the present study is to know what could be the reasons that can motivate youth to commit crimes and what precautions can be taken by us as a teacher, parent and community, which can be useful in preventing this type of tendency. Exploratory research design was used for this study. The samples for this study were 30 respondents who was supposed to be Teachers, Officers from the Juvenile Observation Home, Social Workers and Parents. A Semi-structured Questionnaire was developed to collect data. As a result, it was found out that the major causes that leads children to commit offences are various Adolescence phase, financial instability, Peer pressure, Environmental factors like Family background, parental skills and surroundings etc. and social media also. It is also found that education plays a major role in the formation of beliefs and moral values in the life of a child. Schools and communities should run an awareness campaign together to learn how to engage in positive self-appraisal so that these children can be helped and youth can learn how to deal with conflict and aggression.

Keywords Juvenile, Delinquency, Causes, Prevention.

Introduction

Delinquency is not a new term, crime has been there ever since human civilization, only its types and methods have changed. Any crime which is committed by a child below 18 years is kept in the category of juvenile crime instead of keeping it in the category of crime. There are two types of crimes under juvenile delinquency first status offences and second delinquent offences, status offences are considered as an offence only when it is committed by children below the age of 18 like indiscipline in school, smoking, drinking etc. and delinquent offences are the offences that are considered as a crime when it is committed by all age groups for example murder, theft, assault etc. In today's time, delinquency is seen in every society of the world, no area is untouched by it. India is also not untouched by this problem, Juvenile delinquency rate is continuously increasing here, many efforts have been made continuously by the government to bridge this problem, but there is no complete success in controlling this problem. No one factor is responsible for delinquency, but there are many reasons that motivate a child to commit a crime.

It is to be noted here that no single definition of juvenile delinquent can be fixed because it is difficult to define juvenile delinquent according to the country, time and situation. There is no single definition that is universally applicable to all countries. For example, in America, school bunking, disobeying parents, etc. comes under the category of child crime, and in India, stealing, black marketing, street hawking, molestation, etc. comes under the category of child crime.

These trends are not only in India, but the number of juvenile delinquents is increasing day by day all over the world. Although the government has made efforts in this direction, but these efforts have not been completely successful, the government needs to take some tough decisions so that this serious problem can be solved because the development of the country is based on children, when the pillars of development become weak, then the future will go into darkness and the development of the nation will also be in danger.

Objective of study

Therefore, keeping in mind the research questions, the following objectives have been formed:

1. To study the causes that contribute to juvenile delinquency in India.
2. To study the roles of community program in preventing juvenile delinquency in India.

Review of Literature

According to the law enforcement and juvenile crime (2008) there were about 6,318 youths aged 10-17 who got arrested. In the article by Baruah (June 15, 2016) from The Times Of India reveals that Assam topped the list of Northeastern states with the highest rate of juvenile delinquency followed by Meghalaya while Nagaland registered the lowest numbers of children in conflict with the law since January 2014. The Indian Express (October 22, 2019) reveals the data from the National Crimes Record Bureau (NCRB) where over 40,000 juveniles were caught across the country in 2017 for their alleged involvement in various crimes, with 72 percent belonging to the age of 16-18 years. A total of 31,170 cases have been registered against Juveniles during 2021, depicting an increase of 4.7% over 2020 (29,768 cases). The increasing number of juvenile delinquents forced us to think that what are the reasons in our society which are responsible for juvenile delinquency.

Methodology

Research Questions

1. What are the causes responsible for juvenile delinquency?
2. What is the role of the society and community in preventing juvenile delinquents?

Significance of the Study

As the statistics have been analyzed above that the number of child crimes is increasing day by day and it is becoming a serious problem for any nation. Therefore, it is very important to know that why any child commits crime, what can be the reason which is responsible for child crime. As we are seeing that day by day this problem is taking a serious form for which there is a great need to make efforts to solve it because these children are our future and the progress of the country depends on them. Therefore, through this study we will be able to understand what is the reason for this problem prevalent in the society and what are the possible solutions to overcome it.

Methodology

The area of the study for this research is in Agra and to fulfill the purpose of the study researcher uses exploratory design in this study. By using this study researcher has been able to explore new concepts and ideas to find the expected solutions of this problem. This design also helps to acquire more knowledge about this field. Both male and female from government observational home, social workers, parents and teachers were used as a sample of the present sample. Out of 30 respondents only 22 respondents were answered and out of 22 respondents 10 were teachers, 4 were from government observational home, 6 were parents and 2 were social workers. Researcher contact them by telephonic conversation and tried to send the questionnaire according to their convenience through WhatsApp and emails. After this researcher analysis and interpretate the data.

Result and Discussion

Researcher using Microsoft excel pie chart to describe the socio demographic profile of the participants. Keeping in mind the research ethics researcher ensure that the identity of the respondents will not be revealed at any cost and recording of their responses will be deleted after once researcher completed the study. Here socio demographic details of participants are given below:

Figure 1: 39 % were males and the remaining 61% were females. It was noted that there is a higher number of Female respondents as compared to Male.

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Figure 2: as seen in the figure, out of the 22 respondents interviewed many of the respondents have belonged to different age groups.

Figure 3: Out of 22 respondents interviewed, the highest respondents were teachers (47 %) and the rest were social workers (6%) which is the least, officers from Gov. observational home (19%) and parents (28%).

Figure 4: Out of the respondents interviewed, 82 % of them were Hindus and the 4% Muslims, 5% Christian and rest 9 % were belongs to others religion.

Causes that Responsible for Delinquency are:

There are various causes observed by the researcher that are contributed to delinquency, hence the main objective of our study is to observe the causes of child delinquency in the society which are given below.

Environmental Causes

It has been observed that environmental factors also play an important role in increasing the tendency of delinquency among children. While analyzing the data, it was found that most of the people considered environmental factors responsible for juvenile delinquency. This also includes the family background and behavior of the parents towards the child, like how much attention the parents pay to the child, how much time they give, how they solve the child's problems, etc. Another reason for this tendency to develop in these children is the lack of proper guidance and counseling which should be given to the children by the parents from time to time so that the children can understand the difference between right and wrong. Apart from all this, other environmental factors around the child also impacts the child also lead him for delinquent tendency like neighboring, peer group etc. Some more factors are present

in our environment as social discrimination going on in our society, negligence by society force child into delinquency.

If we are talking about the environment of the child, then how can we forget the school environment which plays an important role in the development of the child. School is a place where a child grows up and learns to distinguish between right and wrong. After the family, if there is any other place that is important for the child, then it is the school, hence most of the respondents have held the school environment responsible for the increasing delinquency in the child, where sometimes due to inferiority complex, sometimes due to peer group pressure, they commit such acts and gradually it takes the form of a habit and delinquency break out. Mishra and Biswal (2018) found in his study that one of the reasons for the increasing number of child delinquency among children is the failure of schools. The poor environment of schools destroys children's interest in learning, children do not get emotional support due to which they are unable to differentiate between right and wrong, hence it is very important for the school environment to be right for the proper development and growth of children. Hehen (2006) revealed in his study that Neighborhood structural, social characteristics, parenting, peer group are directly and indirectly affecting the delinquency tendency in children

Psychological Causes

Psychological reasons of the child are also a reason which promotes the delinquent tendency in children. Psychological aspects of personality such as emotional instability, emotional insecurity, inferiority, jealousy during the adolescence period, etc. Adolescence is a stage in which many physical and mental changes are taking place inside the child and these changes are directly and indirectly responsible for such behavior of children. It is the time when children need love, affection and care and lack of care increase social inequality in children and due to which children turn towards such offences. Apart from all these, if the separation or divorce of the parents happens in front of the child, then it also has a psychological impact on the child. It has also been found in various studies that the parents of most of the delinquent children were either divorced or had some differences among themselves. It also has bad effects on child personality specially on psychological aspects. Machtel Hoeve (2009) explained that parenting is directly related to child delinquency. These children are not catering in proper manner and they feel some kind of insecurity in their life. May be this insecurity provoke them to commit such type of offences. Moitra Tanusree & Mukherjee Indrani (2010) revealed that Parenting style of father and mother directed linked with delinquency.

Economic Causes

Poverty is the major issues in India, for basic need like food, clothes, shelter they have to fight, they have to struggle for that. Many studies revealed that mostly juvenile delinquent committed offence such as theft, murder just to fulfil these urges. One more thing is jealousy, desire for luxurious life. In present time everyone wants luxurious things as well as luxurious life and for that they can even do wrong things. Financial instability leads child into delinquency, it is also revealed by many studies, Chandolu S.R. (2015) observed in his study that poverty was the most important reason for juvenile delinquency. 58.3% of respondents surveyed expressed it

Educational Causes

Education plays an important role in shaping the personality of any child, school is like a second home and teachers are like second parents so after home it is the responsibilities of school to take care of children. Educational institutes should conduct such program that prevent children from such kind of offences. Teacher can mould the life of students, teacher should understand the needs of children, support them and treated them equally. Counselling session should be organized to resolve the psychological needs and various others problem of children. Any-bullying programs to create the awareness among youth. It is necessary to provide moral education and social norms in the school. Value based program should be conducted to inculcate the values in children which will be very helpful in future for these children.

Apart from this, the education of the parents of the children is also as important as the education of the children. Those left in an educated family can learn about right and wrong. These are some factors which are responsible for delinquency in children, an educated parents can give all the necessary information to the children so that this tendency is not encouraged in the children and the children can avoid committing any kind of crime. Therefore, programs related to prevention of juvenile delinquency

should be included in the school curriculum. Ajay Kumar Reddy Babba, D. Bhanu Kiran & Naidana Partha Sarathy (2018) found that illiteracy was the major cause of delinquency in children.

Role of Social-Media

We all are aware of the negative impact of social media and most of the respondents also agree that it has a huge impact on our youth and it also plays a big role in children committing crimes. The influence of the media world is very strong and real and in the present time it has become a medium to confuse the youth due to which the youth commit various types of crimes like bullying, harassment, violent activities like gang related crimes etc. and these crimes mostly against their friends, family members and their relatives. Social media is diverting today's children, who are tomorrow's future, away from their real goals.

Role of Community Program in Preventing Juvenile Delinquency

During the study, when the respondents were asked about the role of the community, most of them said that the community is a major factor that can contribute to preventing crimes. According to Aggarwal D. (2018) when it comes to juvenile delinquency, it is very important to have community participation and sensitivity. For matters related to juvenile delinquency, the findings of various studies show that the main role of the community is to make the youth and family members aware so that the family and community can help the youth in the problems they are going through. Police and social media also have a very important role under the community program. Such awareness campaigns should be run by the police department and through social media. So that the people of the community can become aware and stop youth from committing crimes. We are still trying to negate the influence of social media but social media is a powerful tool which can put the evil spirits of juvenile delinquency in front of the youth in a very good way.

Role of Counseling

Sharma Priti (2020) examined in her study that proper guidance and counselling prevent children to commit offences. Many respondents also accept that counselling is the best way to prevent from delinquency, it is the most effective tool not for only community specially for families to prevent their young souls at an early stage. Through counseling the mind of the child can be understood and child can be helped according to his needs. Effective counselling helps to remove the fear of inferiority complex in children, fear and many other issues that many children are facing present days. Muregasan (2014) examined on 148 juveniles and reveals that 42.6 % of the children liked counselling and some kind of psychological treatment which is one of the effective techniques for prevention of such kind of antisocial behavior in society. Steps should be taken towards this problem from the very beginning, for which a counseling cell should be arranged in every school so that children can get solutions to their problems in the school itself. Apart from this, one of the functions of this counseling cell should also be to make the parents aware and provide help that if they see any such problem in their child or any changes in the behavior of the child, then the parents should know how to support the child and how to prevent from delinquency.

Conclusion At present, we see that crime is increasing very fast in the society and there is a need to prevent it. This is important so that the increase in crimes committed by children can be curbed because these children are our future. The point to be noted here is that children's attitude and behavior mostly depends on their environment. The speech of a child becomes dependent on the environment in which he was born and brought up. So as a community and family we have to take care and it largely depends on us how we help children, how to help them develop the understanding of right and wrong so that they are able to take right decisions. We try to develop positive attitude in their daily life. The findings of the study have revealed some reasons which are responsible for increasing this trend in children such as peer pressure, family social factors, addiction, poverty, influence of social media, etc. and now after seeing these reasons, we have to think how we can stop this delinquent tendency in children as a community and as a family. The findings of the study also revealed that parents need better understanding in mutual behavior and they also need to take care that the family environment should be such where the child can share his problems with the family members. Not only parents have a role in preventing child abuse, but teachers, police and educational institutions also have a major role. To curb crimes, there is a great need for reform in the community and institutions so that the increase of crimes in the society can be stopped. Moral education should be provided to create awareness. Youth are the future representatives of our country; hence it is very important that they get proper guidance from time to time and it is very important for the youth to get awareness for behavior modification from their parents, teachers and counselors.

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